

Hypergraph-based laplacian score for feature selection

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Abstract: The dimensionality reduction problem is introduced as a challenging topic in machine learning when working with high-dimensional data. This issue features a number of notable achievements from recent years. Subspace learning and feature selection approaches are two major kinds of dimensionality reduction methods in this context. Indeed, the effectiveness and efficiency of these algorithms are the distinguishing features that have made them so popular. Subspace learning methods are critical in translating a high-dimensional space into a smaller subspace in the context of dimensionality reduction. Dimensionality reduction has two parts. These two parts are feature selection and feature extraction. Here I have worked with the feature selection. Feature selection method is normally classified into three categories: wrapper feature selection, filter feature selection and embedded feature selection methods. Selecting a set of features by making a use of a learning method in a way that the performance of the classification becomes better in a wrapper method. In order to discover irrelevant features and select a subset of characteristics, the filter methods make use of some ranking criteria and statistical qualities of data. Searching on the relevant features within the learning model being applied in the process of feature selection. Feature Selection through Hypergraph Embedding we can describe here. Here using the representations and where - dimensional vector and its elements represent the samples separately in the t_h dimension of the low dimensional feature space. Based on the hypergraph transformation described and the scheme of Laplacian eigen-decomposition, the hypergraph spectral embedding can be easily conducted as follows. Laplacian feature selection is a novel feature selection filter that is unaffected by the learning task. It may be done with or without supervision. The new method is based on the fact that local geometric structure is important for discrimination. Experiments with the Iris and PIE face datasets show that our approach is successful. Laplacian feature selection uses normal 2D correlation graphs to present their score. This graph is not so efficient to determine the complex features. This feature selection may lose some features of the data. To remedy the information loss issue occurring in the above methodology is to represent the data as a hypergraph.

Keywords: Dimensionality reduction (5), hypergraph (27), Laplacian (26), hyperedge (47), feature selection (70), Laplacian matrix (10).

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Introduction

Traditional feature selection approaches deal with this problem by dividing the original feature set into different clusters based on comparable traits. However, merely examining pairwise relations weakens all of the previous approaches. Higher-order relations are more suitable to the classification job at hand in some cases, and approximating them in terms of pairwise interactions might result in significant information loss. To address the aforementioned issue,

we offer a hypergraph-based technique to feature selection in this study. High-order feature similarities can be detected via hypergraph clustering. The original features are grouped into several groups based on hypergraph clustering in this feature selection technique, with each group containing just a small number of characteristics. A novel feature selection criterion known as multidimensional interaction information is also used to feature selection for each group. Hypergraph clustering simultaneously considers the significance of both the features and the correlation between features, and therefore the structural information concealed in the data can be more effectively utilized.

By including a Laplacian regularizer into the framework of sparse feature selection, it is hypothesized that unsupervised spectral feature selection (USFS) concurrently incorporate interpretability and discriminative ability [1][2]. For instance, the two-step USFS techniques, independently learn the original data's graph representation and perform feature selection [3][4]. Due to the fact that the first stage of two-step USFS methods—learning graph representation—is learning graph representation rather than performing feature selection, it cannot assist the second step, which is the process of feature selection. Additionally, a strong Laplacian matrix is difficult to produce since it must be learned from the original data, which often includes duplicate features. One-step USFS algorithms are created to concurrently learn the Laplacian matrix and perform feature selection in a single framework in order to overcome these problems [5][6][7]. As a result, until both of them are stable, or reaching convergence, the Laplacian matrix and the chosen features are updated repeatedly. The Laplacian matrix is learned using a broad graph, but earlier one-step USFS algorithms only concentrate on this, making it unable to capture intricate relationships between the samples [8][9].

In this paper I have proposed a feature selection method that uses hypergraph to reduce the feature selection score. Here I tried to construct the feature selection with the hypergraph. The hypergraph reduces the feature selection score that makes more valuable information with low data dimension.

Research Methodology

Subspace learning converts high-dimensional data into a low-dimensional space while keeping key information (such as sample geometric organization). Linear approaches (such as principal component analysis (PCA), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), and locality preserving projection (LPP)) and non-linear methods (such as kernel PCA, kernel LDA, and kernel LPP) are some of the most well-known subspace learning techniques. PCA maintains the maximum variance, whereas LDA preserves both the lowest and maximum variance within a class. Feature selection is a prominent technique for dealing with the problem of high-dimensional data. It is an interpretable model that selects useful characteristics from the original features. Filter models, wrapper models, and embedding models are the three subcategories of traditional feature selection approaches [10] [11]. Sparse feature selection is an embedded model that may be expressed as:

$$\min_s f(P) + \theta(P) \quad (1)$$

Where $f(p)$ a sparse penalty is term and $\theta(p)$ is a loss function. The least square loss function, robust loss function, hinge loss, and other popular loss functions are just a few examples. The V_1 norm regularizer [12], the $V_{2,1}$ -norm regularizer [10][13], and the $V_{2,\infty}$ norm regularizer are all part of the sparse regularizer [14]. The informative features corresponding to nonzero elements or rows in the transformation matrix are kept after the sparse feature selection is completed.

In general, subspace learning produces a discriminative model, while feature selection produces an interpretable model. USFS combines subspace learning and feature selection to produce a discriminative and interpretable model by embedding a Laplacian regularizer in an unsupervised framework of sparse feature selection [15]. To retain the local structure of data, Liu et al. embeds a Laplacian matrix in the sparse feature selection model. Initially, a hypergraph is constructed using the k-nearest neighbor approach to preserve the high-order local connection of samples, and then a Laplacian matrix is built using this hyper graph to perform feature selection [16].

Learning with a fixed general-graph

Graph is widely used to preserve sample geometric structures and enhance dimension reduction achievement. An edge connect the two data points m_i and m_j will be generated if m_i is one of m_j 's k nearest neighbors (kNN). This edge's weight can be determined by:

$$Q_{i,j} = \begin{cases} e^{-\frac{\|m_i - m_j\|_2^2}{2\sigma^2}}, & m_i \text{ is one of kNN of } m_j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where, σ is a tuning parameter. LPP is a traditional methodology [17] that uses a similarity measures to preserve local structure of samples in order to create the general graph once only (i.e., fixed general-graph) by:

$$\min_s \sum_{i,j} \|P^T m_i - P^T m_j\|_2^2 Q_{i,j} \Leftrightarrow \min_s \text{tr}(P^T M W X^T P) \quad (3)$$

Here P is the transformation matrix and $P^T M$ is the estimated feature space. $W = F - M$ is the Laplacian matrix and F is a diagonal matrix which diagonal element $F_{i,j}$ is bounded as $F_{i,j} = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{i,j}$. The local structure of the source data in predicted feature space can be preserved since the conditional probability M evaluates the similarity of two samples with a generic graphs. To achieve unsupervised feature selection, Eq. (3) is usually embedded within in the feature selection framework in Eq. (1) [18][19][9].

Hypergraph learning

General-graph approaches retain the local features of training sets by using pair-wise connections among training data, but have been shown to be inadequate to capture complex relationships in training dataset [2]. The author-paper relationship is depicted in Fig. 1, where the left sub-figure employs a broad graph to illustrate the author-pair relationship by measuring the relationship between two samples. As an example a_1 vs a_2 , a_2 vs a_3 , and a_2 vs. a_4 . Therefore, implying the link we may truly focus on, i.e., the first work having three authors, is tough. And the second paper has two authors. The right sub-figure of Fig. 1 on the other hand, by generating a hypergraph, clearly shows these two sorts of relationships. As a result, the focus of this research is on employing a hypergraph to maintain the local structures of training data, as a hypergraph may record more intricate data relationships than a general-graph [20].

Fig. 1: Illustration of the difference of hypergraph and normal graph

The right sub-figure of Fig. 1 on the other hand, by creating a hypergraph, clearly indicates these two types of relationships. As a consequence, the focus of this paper is on using a hypergraph to maintain the natural structures of training data, as a hypergraph can catch more complex data relationships than a general-graph. The term "hypergraph" is used to describe a network of hypergraphs $G = (R, F, w)$, where $R = [u_1, \dots, u_n]$ and $F = [e_1, \dots, e_n]$ are the set of vertices and hyper-edges, respectively, and the weight of hyper-edges is $w = [w_1, \dots, w_n]$, and the building of a hypergraph consists of three steps. (i) the recurrence matrix Z, which represents the binary vertex-edge connection and has the following elements:

$$H(u_i, e_j) = \begin{cases} 1, & u_i \in e_j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

(ii) The hypergraph Laplacian \mathbf{W} , i.e. the hyper-normalized graph's Laplacian matrix, (iii) and the weighting factor \mathbf{w} , which measures the relevance of hyper-edges.

Unlike a conventional graph, which each edge indicates the vertex-to-vertex relationship, every edge in this diagram represents the vertex-to-vertex connection. The vertex-to-hyperedge connection is described by the incidence matrix \mathbf{H} of a hypergraph. To do so, first, take a look at the training data $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times n}$ where c and n is the number of the features and the sample [20].

Using the following formula we generate the hyperedge e_i by

$$e_i = \{u_i \mid \theta(m_i, x_j) \leq 0.1\sigma_i\}, i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

where $\theta(m_i, m_j)$ denotes the level of correlation between m_i and m_j (e.g., Euclidean distance in this case), and σ_i is the arithmetic mean between m_i and each of the other instances Above that the threshold approach is widely used for hyperedge creation, and clearly accomplishes the scenario when distinct samples have varied numbers of nearest neighbors, as opposed to prior methods, which set the same number of nearest neighbors to all samples.

Next, The relevance of each hyperedge is determined using the resultant incidence matrix \mathbf{H} and the training data, i.e., \mathbf{w} . Following that, we acquire the degree $\delta(e_i)$ of a hyperedge e_i via $\delta(e_i) = \sum_{u_j \in F} g(u_j, e_i)$ and the degree

$$k(u_i) \text{ of a vertex } u_j \text{ via } k(u_j) = \sum_{u_j \in e_i, e_j \in F} w(e_i) g(u_j, e_i).$$

Then, the Hypergraph based Laplacian matrix is structured by:

$$W = I - F_u^{-\frac{1}{2}} Z Q F_e^{-1} Z^T F_u^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

where, $I \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is an identity matrix, F_e , F_u and \mathbf{w} , respectively, are the diagonal matrices $\delta = [\delta(e_i)]$, $k = [k(u_j)]$ and $w = [w(e_i)]$.

Now we have constructed a hypergraph laplacian by the equation (6) to maintain the relationship among no less than two samples. Laplacian Score with Hypergraph Embedding let w_r denotes the laplacian score of the r -th r -th feature. Let f_{ri} denote the i -th sample of the r -th feature, $i = 1, \dots, m$. Algorithm can be describe as: Construct a nearest neighbor graph G with m nodes. The i -th node corresponds to x_i . We put an edge between nodes i and j if x_i and x_j are "close", i.e. x_i is among k nearest neighbors of x_j or x_j is among k nearest neighbors of x_i . When the label information is available, one can put an edge between two nodes sharing the same label. If nodes i and j are connected, put $s_{ij} = e^{-\frac{\|x_i - x_j\|^2}{t}}$, where t is a suitable constant. Otherwise, put $s_{ij} = 0$. The weight matrix S of the graph models the local structure of the data space [30]. For the r -th feature, we define: $f_r = [f_{r1}, f_{r2}, \dots, f_{rm}]^T$, $F = \text{diag}(S1)$, $\mathbf{1} = [1, \dots, 1]^T$, $W = F - R$ where the matrix W is graph Laplacian and the matrix L is often called graph Laplacian [22].

$$\text{Let, } \tilde{f}_r = f_r - \frac{f_r^T W \mathbf{1}}{\mathbf{1}^T W \mathbf{1}} \mathbf{1} \quad (7)$$

For the r -th the laplacian score is as follows:

$$W_r = \frac{\tilde{f}_r^T W \tilde{f}_r}{\tilde{f}_r^T F \tilde{f}_r} \quad (8)$$

From the equation (6) we got the hypergraph laplacian matrix, using the hypergraph laplacian to feature score:

$$W_r = \frac{\tilde{f}_r^T (I - F_u^{-\frac{1}{2}} Z Q F_e^{-1} Z^T F_u^{-\frac{1}{2}}) \tilde{f}_r}{\tilde{f}_r^T F \tilde{f}_r} \quad (9)$$

The source data's local relationships can be preserved using a hypergraph structure. A dynamical general-graph in one-step USFS techniques, but in the other hand, has been utilized to overcome the issue of two-step USPS methods, *i.e.*, conducting similarities learning and feature selection independently. In this research, we suggest that by dynamically training a hypergraph, we can retain the local hypergraph structure of training data while also solving the issue of two-step USFS approaches. To do this, we create the objective function below.

$$P^T M M^T S = I \min_{e \in F, m_i, m_j \in R} \Delta \left\| \frac{P^T m_i}{\sqrt{k(m_i)}} - \frac{P^T m_j}{\sqrt{k(m_j)}} \right\|_2^2 \quad (10)$$

Where $\Delta = \frac{w(e)h(m_i, e)h(m_j, e)}{\sigma(e)}$ and $P \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times c}$ is the transformation matrix. Certainly equation (9) is equivalent

to:

$$P^T M M^T P = I \min_{P^T M M^T P = I} tr(P^T M W M^T P) \quad (11)$$

Where the orthogonal constraint $P^T M M^T P = I$ is implicitly applied, subspace learning is performed, preserving the global structure of the training data.

Objective Function

In Section, there are three consecutive components for the production of a hypergraph. As a result, the quality of either Q or W is determined by Z . Z , on the other hand, is learned from the original training data, which is frequently noisy and redundant. In most cases, the low-quality Z is unable to produce the high-quality W , preventing Eq. (9) from efficiently reducing feature dimensions. In this study, we use a unified framework to combine the learning of hypergraph Z with the learning of P . We want to improve each of them repeatedly by correcting the other, such that they are dynamically updated to provide the best Z and P . To do this, we create the following final goal function for our method:

$$\min_{P, Z, Q} \sum_{e \in F, m_i, m_j \in R} \Delta \left\| \frac{P^T m_i}{\sqrt{k(m_i)}} - \frac{P^T m_j}{\sqrt{k(m_j)}} \right\| + \alpha \|M\|_E^2 + \beta \|P\|_{2,1} \quad (12)$$

s.t., $Q^T \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1}, w_i > 0, P^T M M^T P = I$ we can convert equation (11) directly to:

$$\min_{P, Z, Q} tr(P^T M W M^T P) + \alpha \|Q\|_E^2 + \beta \|P\|_{2,1} \quad (13)$$

s.t., $Q^T \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1}, w_{i,i} > 0, P^T M M^T P = I$ Where α and β are two tuning parameters, and $\mathbf{1}$ is a vector with 1 as its members. The constraint $P^T M M^T P = I$ really performs subspace learning to make the feature selection discriminative, whereas $v_{2,1}$ -norm pushes for row sparsity to pick informative features [23] [24]. In Fig. 2, we depict the differences between our proposed techniques and earlier feature selection methods, and we summaries the contributions of our suggested method in the following order. First, our technique in Eq. (13) combines subspace learning and feature selection into a unified framework, in which subspace learning and feature selection may give complimentary information to each other, removing noise and redundancy from various aspects [25][25]. Previous approaches, on the other hand, solely used these two methods, and additional methods, to conduct subspace learning and feature selection individually[27][28]. Second, with low-dimensional training data, our technique retains both the local and global structures. It's worth noting that prior techniques, retain the original data's local structures [25] [26]. Third, unlike previous approaches, which learn a fixed hypergraph from the original training data in order to retain high-order local structures [21], our proposed method learns a dynamic hypergraph using low-dimensional training data.

Result and Analysis

Clustering Analysis results: We compared our proposed hypergraph-based technique to comparable methods in terms of clustering tasks on twelve available UCI datasets in this section, listing the clustering accuracy of all methods with varied numbers of chosen features.

Fig. 2: Illustration of the difference of hypergraph and normal graph

On most datasets, our method outperformed JHLRSR, SOGFS, CDLFS, MRFS, LS, and Baseline in terms of clustering performance. For example, as compared to the weakest approach (Baseline) and the best comparison method, our method improved by 5.38 percent and 2.01 percent, respectively (i.e., JHLRSR). The explanation for this could be that our method 1) combines subspace learning and feature selection in a single framework, and 2) learns the hypergraph from low-dimensional training data in order to capture the training data's high-order local structure [29]. We can also see in Fig 2 that the original data contains redundant and unnecessary characteristics, implying that dimensionality reduction is required before doing cluster activities. To begin with, all of the feature selection approaches performed better than Baseline. On all datasets, for example, LS (the worst feature selection approach) improved by 3.03 percent on average over Baseline. Second, as the number of feature dimensions increased, the clustering accuracy of all feature selection approaches improved. After reaching the apex, clustering accuracy began to deteriorate or possibly become unstable. On dataset CLL-SUB, for example, clustering accuracy climbed to 55.7 percent while keeping 60 percent of features, then reduced to 52.0 percent when keeping 80 percent of features. This pattern suggests that a small number of features cannot adequately explain learning models, yet an excessively high number of features may introduce redundant features, lowering clustering performance. Each image's segmentation result is depicted in Fig. 3 and the matching segmentation performance is presented in Table 1. Our approach efficiently separated the background and the target participants, according to the findings. In the picture vehicle, for example, our approach was the only one that could totally separate the target item from the backdrop. When compared to other approaches, the target subject segmented by our suggested method was the most comprehensive in the picture deer. It's possible that this is because our technique uses dynamical hypergraph learning to retain data's local structure from many perspectives (such as subspace learning and feature selection).

Fig. 3: on photos, the performance of feature selection approaches in terms of segmentation.

Table. 1 The segmentation result

Deer	PRI	0.5698	0.5698	0.8096	0.5698	0.7301	0.8258	0.8629
	VOI	3.0075	3.007	1.3657	3.0075	2.5925	1.2761	1.0484
	GCE	0.5882	0.5882	0.2137	0.2137	0.4786	0.1714	0.1127
Starfish	PRI	0.6168	0.6617	0.7005	0.6522	0.6887	0.6787	0.7206
	VOI	3.4283	3.4001	2.2741	3.4300	2.6921	2.5150	2.5592
	GCE	0.5406	0.4931	0.39192	0.4957	0.3375	0.3549	0.3383

Conclusion

In this paper we have tested with simple image file. The practice result is expectedly satisfied. The hypergraph is used in this paper to capture the rich structure of low-dimensional training data while removing duplicate and unnecessary features. In terms of clustering tasks and image segmentation tasks, experimental findings on benchmark datasets confirmed the efficacy and robustness of our strategy when compared to state-of-the-art feature selection methods. We want to expand hypergraph learning to directly execute clustering tasks without employing k-means clustering in future work.

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